

Editorial Acknowledgment

This issue features two regular articles and one article that is an extended version of a paper presented at the [16th International Conference on Educational Data Mining \(EDM\)](#) that took place in Bengaluru, India, July 11-14 2024, and published in the [conference's proceedings](#).

For the second time, the EDM conference and JEDM coordinated to invite several of the most outstanding papers from the conference to submit extended versions of those papers for publication as articles in JEDM. This process affords authors the opportunity to update and expand their most promising research, including analyses and discussions that would not have fit into the constraints of the conference proceedings page limits. In total, the authors of seven papers were invited based on positive reviews and clear opportunities for beneficial extension; the authors of five papers accepted the invitation and submitted extended articles for review. These submissions were reviewed by a mix of individuals who had reviewed the original EDM submissions as well as new reviewers. Four extended articles are still under review and may be published in the next issue of JEDM if accepted.

We thank the reviewers who volunteered their time and effort to provide feedback on these articles.

This issue also includes, for the first time, articles published in both PDF and HTML formats. The HTML format improves accessibility for people using screen readers, including alt text descriptions of figures. Additionally, HTML versions of papers are more readily indexed by search engines, potentially improving the discoverability and impact of research in JEDM. Future issues of JEDM will include accessible versions of all articles (contributions to the [paper format conversion project](#) are welcome).

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